

CLIMATE DISINFORMATION ON GOOGLE SEARCH

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The year 2024 had the highest temperatures ever recorded (Copernicus, 2025). The accelerating climate crisis demands urgent action, but disinformation continues to spread, delaying and obstructing necessary measures (IPCC, 2023; Bakowicz, 2024).

Google searches for "net zero" or "greenhouse gas" emissions often yield results funded by fossil fuel companies (Oehlenschläger, 2022). Companies have successfully delayed climate action by promoting themselves as eco-friendly (Ahmed, 2021). This is a type of climate disinformation known as greenwashing.

Users trust Google Search to provide reliable and accurate information (Lewandowski & Schultheiß, 2022), which the company claims to do through the principle of trustworthiness, EEAT and YMYL (Google, 2025).

PURPOSE

This study aims to improve the understanding of how Google Search contributes to greenwashing as a form of climate disinformation.

The following research questions are addressed:

1. Does Google Search contribute to making greenwashing visible, and if so, how?
2. How can the results be understood against the background of Google's principle of trustworthiness?

DEFINITIONS

Climate Disinformation: false or misleading information about the climate crisis, its origins and possible solutions (CAAD, n.d.).

Greenwashing: disinformation in which companies make exaggerated or false claims to appear more environmentally sustainable when their activities contribute to climate change and other environmental harm (European Parliament, 2024; Ekberg et al., 2023; Naderer, Schmuck & Matthes, 2017).

EEAT (Experience, Expertise, Authoritativeness, and Trustworthiness): A Google principle used to assess website quality and credibility to rank search results (Google, 2025).

YMYL (Your Money or Your Life): websites with health, economic, or social implications. Pages classified as YMYL may cause harm if not trustworthy, requiring careful review by human quality evaluators. Trustworthiness is evaluated using Google's EEAT principles. Web pages covered by YMYL that do not meet Google's principles of trustworthiness receive a lower ranking from quality evaluators (Google, 2025).

METHODS

The study is based on an Algorithm audit: Structured review of Google Search ranking algorithms.

The data collection was performed by the search engine scraper, Result Assessment Tool (RAT). The data contained; the 20 first results of each query, creation date and time, url, main website, position in the SERP, title and description of the search results.

Five companies publicly accused of greenwashing; Arla, Preem, H&M, Shell and Shein were used in the study. The companies represent three different sectors that account for a large share of global emissions (RCO, 2024); the food industry, the fossil fuel industry and the textile industry. The companies are used as an indicator of greenwashing on Google Search.

A content analysis with a coding scheme was used to analyze the individual search results. Frame theory was used to analyze the individual search results and the search engine result page (SERP) as a whole to understand which perspectives of the query that are presented and what is missing in the SERP.

GREENWASHING CRITERIA

Seven criteria were used to detect greenwashing in the data (Preemwashing, n.d; Terrachoice, 2010).

1. selective information (G1)
2. lack of evidence (G2)
3. vagueness (G3)
4. irrelevance (G4)
5. the best of two negative things (G5)
6. lies, false advertisement (G6)
7. unreasonable future promises (G7)

Search queries

"climate neutral"
"net zero emissions"
"Arla sustainability"
"H&M sustainability"
"Shell sustainability"
"Shein sustainability"
"Preem sustainability"

Coding scheme

Greenwashing (G)
Critical review (C)
Information (I)
Marketing (M)
News media (N)
Science (S)

RESULT

Position in SERP	Climate neutral	Net zero emissions	Arla Sustainability	H&M Sustainability	Preem Sustainability	Shein Sustainability	Shell Sustainability
1	G3, G7	I	G5, G7	G1, G5	G3, G7	G7	G1, G3
2	G3, G5	G1	G5, G7	G5, G7	G5, G7	C	G3, G7
3	M	C	G5, G7	G1, G7	I	C	G3
4	M	I	C	G3, G7	I	C	C
5	I	I	M	N	M	G1, G5	C
6	M	I	M	M	N	G7	G3
7	G2, G3	I	C	C	C	C	I
8	G2, G4 & G7	M	M	S	G7	N	C
9	M	I	M	M	G1	M	C
10	M	M	M	G3, G7	G1, G3, G7	C	G3
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11	G5	I	M	C	G3, G7	C	G3, G7
12	G3, G7	M	M	C	G7	C	M
13	I	M	M	M	N	C	G3
14	I	M	M	S	N	C	M
15	I	M	C	S	I	C	G3
16	I	G7	G5, G7	G3, G7	G5	C	M
17	I	G1, G5	C	G1	G1, G5	C	M
18	M	G5, G7	C	C	G7	C	G1, G7
19	G2, G5	S	M	M	N	N	C
20	G2, G3	N	M	C	N	G2, G3	G1, G3, G7

Above is an overview of the result. The chart shows each queries with the 20 first results and the positions in the SERP. The search results have been coded according to the above coding scheme.

In four of the seven queries, possible greenwashing and marketing content was the most common result in the SERP. Critical reviews and scientific information were generally missing on the first result page.

DISCUSSION

In five of the seven queries the first two to three results of the SERP were of possible greenwashing. This is problematic as studies show that the majority of users only read the first three results of the SERP (Lewandowski, 2023).

Research shows that it takes about thirty seconds for a people to be influenced by greenwashing (Friedman & Campbell, 2023).

When greenwashing is positioned in the first results of the SERP, a frame is created of the companies and their products as sustainable.

What responsibility does Google Search have as a search engine and gatekeeper of information to provide accurate and trustworthy information about the climate crisis, its causes and possible solutions?

CONCLUSION

1. Google Search contribute to the visibility of greenwashing by positioning greenwashing content high in the result page. This may be due to lack of moderation and that commercial interests are premiered.

2. The climate crisis can be framed as a public health issue (Vilhelmsson, 2024). Websites with climate claims that affect people's economy or health therefore ought to be moderated as YMYL and according to the principles of EEAT.

Reference list including sources like: Lewandowski, 2023; Terrachoice, 2010; CAAD, n.d.; IPCC, 2023; Bakowicz, 2024; Oehlenschläger, 2022; Ahmed, 2021; RCO, 2024; Ekberg et al., 2023; Naderer, Schmuck & Matthes, 2017; Friedman & Campbell, 2023; Vilhelmsson, 2024; Google, 2025.